

INDUCTION OF VISCOSITY INCREASE DURING POLYGLYCOL ADDITION TO ISOCYANATES

Paulina Nemaniūtė^{1*}, Dalia Bražinskienė¹, Svajus Asadauskas¹

¹ Department of Chemical Engineering and Technology, FTMC, Vilnius, Lithuania
paulina.nemaniute@ftmc.lt

Two-component polyurethane adhesives often require accurate viscosity control for curing. When mixing the components, polyols engage into addition reaction with isocyanates, which increases mol. wt. resulting in higher viscosity and solidification. Multifunctional additives can be employed to assure cross-linking. However, viscosity does not necessarily increase in parallel with polymerization and such discrepancy cannot be easily explained. In this study, an oligomeric ether-ester macro diol (EEMD of 2700 g/mol) was used as a polyol, diluting it with polyethylene glycols (PEG of 200 g/mol or 400 g/mol) for viscosity control. The polyols were mixed with a trifunctional adduct of hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI3) to initiate the addition reaction and viscosity was monitored, similarly to the previous report [1].

A rotary viscometer Lamy CP-2000 Plus was used with a 1° cone spindle RM100. Beforehand, EEMD was premixed with PEG and heated separately at 50°C for 15 minutes, as was HDI3. The polyol was mixed with HDI3 at 1+1.4 mol ratio. Within 1 min a 1 mL sample was placed onto a bottom plate of the viscometer, which was preheated to 50°C. The upper spindle was lowered and viscosity was periodically recorded at 100 s⁻¹ shear rate. The full rotational (not oscillatory) trajectory was used and the spindle was not removed from the plate until the end of the polymerization test. Three blends were tested: w/o PEG (EEMD at 83.25%+ HDI3 at 16.75% wt/wt), with PEG 200 (at 12.1%+ EEMD at 48.5% + HDI3 at 39.4%) and with PEG 400 (at 22.3% + EEMD at 41.4% + HDI3 at 36.3%). Two runs were performed for each blend, see average values in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Left: structures of employed compounds for addition reaction. Right: viscosity change during the reaction between HDI3 and EEMD (with or without PEG); filled symbols denote viscosities, higher than the early values.

Counter-intuitively, all the blends showed some thinning initially. The drop in viscosity was the most evident in the PEG-free blend. On the other hand, this blend was more viscous than the other two. Nevertheless, its polymerization proceeded slower as a result of lower HDI3 concentration and during the later stages viscosity of PEG 200 blend became more similar. The initial viscosity drop was also evident in the blends with PEG. After the drop, viscosity stagnated or was slowly recovering for quite some time. Only well after 1 hr of polymerization viscosities finally exceeded the initial values, which were measured in the beginning of the test. Further viscosity increase approximately followed linear kinetics, with trendline correlations of the average values better than $R^2 = 0.938$.

This suggests that some induction period is present before viscosity begins increasing despite ongoing polymerization. It remains unclear, which factors might cause such induction effect. Inclusion of PEG seems to enhance the effect, because the PEG-free blend simply thinned down initially and began thickening quite soon. Bubble formation or compositional non-homogeneities in the blend are not likely to have a strong effect, since the blends were agitated quite vigorously between the cone and plate of the viscometer when measuring each point.

It might be possible that supramolecular arrangements could yield the observed induction of viscosity increase. However, more diverse formulations, extensive testing and additional analytical techniques might be needed to further elaborate on this hypothesis.

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[1] S. Mačiulytė, P. Nemaniūtė, D. Bražinskienė et al., Influence of ester diluents and chain extension on polyurethane viscosities. Proc. of 22nd Conf. Advanced Materials and Technologies, ISSN 1822-7759, pg 128, Palanga, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4064006 (2020).

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P. Nemaniutė^{1*}, D. Bražinskienė¹, S. J. Asadauskas¹

¹ Center for Physical Sciences and Technology (FTMC), Saulėtekio 3, LT-10257, Vilnius, Lithuania

* paulina.nemaniute@ftmc.lt

Fig. 1 Multilayer film for food packaging [4]

INTRODUCTION

In food industry multilayer packaging is broadly used, often laminated with polyurethane (PU) adhesives, Fig. 1. Most frequently, PU plastics are obtained from two components: 1) macrodiols and 2) isocyanates and those two components reacting with each other forms urethane linkages. Two-component polyurethane adhesives often require accurate viscosity control for curing. When mixing the components, polyols engage into addition reaction with isocyanates, which increases mol. wt. resulting in higher viscosity and solidification. Multifunctional additives can be employed to assure cross-linking. However, viscosity does not necessarily increase in parallel with polymerization and such discrepancy cannot be easily explained.

Fig. 2 Laminator K PRINTING PROOFER used in laboratory for multilayer packaging

MATERIALS

In this study, an oligomeric ether-ester macro diol (EEMD of 2700 g/mol) was used as a polyol, diluting it with polyethylene glycols (PEG of 200 g/mol or 400 g/mol) for viscosity control, see Scheme A. The polyols were mixed with a trifunctional adduct of hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI3) to initiate the addition reaction and viscosity was monitored, similarly to the previous report [1]. Three blends were tested: w/o PEG (EEMD at 83.25% + HDI3 at 16.75% wt/wt), with PEG 200 (at 12.1% + EEMD at 48.5% + HDI3 at 39.4%) and with PEG 400 (at 22.3% + EEMD at 41.4% + HDI3 at 36.3%).

Fig. 3 Rotary rheometer used in the study

EXPERIMENTAL

A rotary viscometer Lamy CP-2000 Plus was used with a 1° cone spindle RM100, see Fig. 3. Beforehand, EEMD was premixed with PEG and heated separately at 50°C for 15 minutes, as was HDI3. The polyol was mixed with HDI3 at 1+1.4 mol ratio. Within 1 min a 1 mL sample was placed onto a bottom plate of the viscometer, which was preheated to 50°C. The upper spindle was lowered and viscosity was periodically recorded at 100 s⁻¹ shear rate. The full rotational (not oscillatory) trajectory was used, and the spindle was not removed from the plate until the end of the polymerization test. Two runs were performed for each blend.

RESULTS (1)

The influence of PEG 200 and PEG 400 diluents on dynamic viscosity of EEMD blends was measured at 50°C. The results are shown in Fig. 5. Higher amounts of diluents decreased viscosity. Fig. 5 also includes PEG 400 viscosity of 29 mPa·s at 50°C and PEG 200 viscosity of 19.7 mPa·s at 50°C from elsewhere [2][3]. Higher amounts of EEMD shows that viscosities of blends are very similar. As we see in Fig. 5, the semilog correlation was very well with both diluents.

Fig. 5 Influence of PEG 200 and PEG 400 diluent on dynamic viscosity of EEMD blends at 50°C

RESULTS (2)

Counter-intuitively, all the blends showed some thinning initially, see Fig. 6. The drop in viscosity was the most evident in the PEG-free blend. On the other hand, this blend was more viscous than the other two. Nevertheless, its polymerization proceeded slower as a result of lower HDI3 concentration and during the later stages viscosity of PEG 200 blend became more similar. The initial viscosity drop was also evident in the blends with PEG. After the drop, viscosity stagnated or was slowly recovering for quite some time. Only well after 1 hr of polymerization viscosities finally exceeded the initial values, which were measured in the beginning of the test. Further viscosity increase approximately followed linear kinetics, with trendline correlations of the average values better than R² = 0.938.

Fig. 6 Viscosity change during the reaction between HDI3 and EEMD (with or without PEG); filled symbols denote viscosities, higher than the early values

CONCLUSIONS

- Viscosity of PEG blends inexplicably drops despite ongoing polyaddition with isocyanates.
- It might be possible that supramolecular arrangements could yield the observed induction of viscosity increase.
- Further research is needed with more diverse formulations and additional analytical techniques

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MEASUREMENT OF STORAGE MODULUS IN UNCURED ELASTOMERS USING PLATE-PLATE AND MOVING DIE TECHNIQUES

Audrė Kalinauskaitė¹, Marijus Jurkūnas^{1,2}, Svajus Asadauskas¹

¹ Department of Chemical Engineering and Technologies, Center for Physical Sciences and Technology, Lithuania

² Faculty of Chemistry and Geoscience, Vilnius University, Lithuania

audre.kalinauskaite@ftmc.lt

Development of new elastomers and their recycling technology is often focused on rheological properties, dynamic moduli in particular [1]. A number of methods can be used for their measurement, primarily highlighting the dependence of storage modulus G' on strain, temperature and other factors. Plate-plate and moving die techniques are often employed. Despite different sample sizes and topography, the techniques exert similar stress onto the elastomer and record the same factors as feedback. This study attempts to compare G' , recorded by both techniques on same elastomers. Non-vulcanized Isoprene Rubber (IR) was used to simulate the elastomer with or without squalane (SQ) at 13% wt. as a plasticizer.

Storage modulus G' was measured using the two techniques tuned to operate under similar thermal and mechanical regimes. Plate-plate technique employed a MCR 302 rheometer with \varnothing 8 mm spindle PP08 (Anton Paar). Temperature sweep was carried out under 0.5% strain at 1 Hz with 5 min preheating for each temperature. Frequency sweeps were taken progressively at 25°C, 100°C and 120°C with 5 min preheating under 0.5% strain, total duration of ~2 h. Load was constant at 1 N. The elastomer samples were pre-cut into \varnothing 8.5 ± 0.5 mm discs 0.5 ± 0.1 mm thick. Moving die technique employed D-MDR 3000 rheometer (Montech, Germany) with biconical dies per ASTM D6204, guarded by disposable polymer sheets. Strain sweep (0.02 – 90% range, 3 cycles for each angle under 1 Hz) and frequency sweep (0.01 – 50 Hz range, 3 cycles for each frequency under 0.5% strain) were carried concurrently on the same specimen at 25°C, 100°C and 120°C with 5 min preheating and total duration of 2 h per sample. Temperature sweep (25 – 120°C with 5°C step every 1.4 min under 1 Hz and 0.5% strain) was performed on different specimens. In both techniques the attempts were made to avoid bubbles, wrinkles or other imperfections, however perfect adherence to plate surface could not be assured. Built-in software calculated G' whose values were processed from multiple runs using Origin software to derive error bars. The most representative curves are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Variation of storage modulus G' due to increasing strain or temperature (top) or frequency (bottom). Plate-plate (MCR) or moving die (MDR) rheometers were used.

Temperature effects on non-plastified IR appear inexplicably opposite. Despite these and other differences in recorded values, tendencies of G' dependence on frequency and plastification appear similar and match expectations. It can be noted that frequency sweep at 120°C by the plate-plate technique matches results from other researchers quite well [1]. Therefore, both techniques can be instrumental in evaluation of rheological properties of elastomers and composites.

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